

THE HEALING AND MEDICINE USES OF KOVRAK PLANT

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ABSTRACT

Kovrak plant is one of the medicinal plants known since ancient times. Studying the medicinal properties of the kovrak plant and developing new methods of extracting its substances will be an added contribution to our medicine.

Key words: *blanket, celeriacs, coumarin, ether, chloroform*

Purpose of work. Identifying the kovrak plant and its healing properties. Distribution areas of the plant, what diseases it is used for, its cultivation, what types are used, countries where it is distributed. Identifying the substances found in the carpet and carrying out qualitative reactions.

Results: Kovrak (ferula) belongs to the family of perennial plants belonging to the family Apiceae (Umbelliferae). It has a pungent smell, it blooms in March-April, the fruit ripens in April-May, it reaches 1-3 meters in height, the root is turnip-like, 15 cm in diameter. The stem is erect, hollow inside, and the upper part is branched. The fruit is bilobed and grows in the deserts. Medicines used for asthma, oncological diseases, and nervous diseases are prepared from the glue (resin) extracted from the root.

Approximately 50% of drugs produced in pharmaceutical enterprises worldwide are made from medicinal plants. Kovarak glue (resin) in folk medicine: Preventing cataracts in eye diseases, removing kidney stones, skin cleansing diseases, skin rashes,

treating infertility, cleaning the liver, arthritic diseases, epilepsy, nervous diseases, treating oncological diseases, pulmonary tuberculosis, plague, whooping cough, to improve the immune system, to treat wounds, toothaches and other diseases, and in scientific medicine, carpet glue (resin), emulsion and tincture (nastayoka), tincture, pill strength. It is used as a stimulant, expectorant and anthelmintic, analgesic and sedative and is included in the pharmacopoeia of many countries.

Grandfather Ibn Sina described: "If you drink 50 g of the decoction of kovrak seeds (the seeds are similar in color and shape to those of a broom), the mother's milk will increase. If eaten with fig juice, it cures yellow hepatitis. Pepper and vinegar are added to the paste and applied to the wounds. It is also useful against hair loss. More than 170 species of carpet grow on the earth, 110 species in Central Asian republics, 50 species in Uzbekistan. In our country: Tashkent, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, Jizzakh, Navoi, Bukhara. 2 types are used for resin-glue production: 1) Sassik kovarak (asafidita), 2) Kohistan kovarak: every organ of kovarak seed, fruit, root, and leaf contains useful substances for human health. The glue (resin) inside the root is mainly used. Qualitative reactions can be used to identify undetected medicinal substances contained in the cruciferous plant. For example: Qualitative reaction to coumarin found in some plants. Lactones derived from coumarin (cis-ortho-oxidolchin) acid and obtained from plants are called coumarins. Cis-ortho-oxydolcinic acid and its derivatives are not found in almost pure form in nature. The acid quickly turns into the corresponding lactone by separating a molecule of water from itself.

Coumarins are Celery-Apiaceae (Umbelliferea), Rutaceae, Leguminaceae (Fabaceae), Lamiaceae (Labiatar), Asteraceae (Compositae), Caryophyllaceae, Solanaceae, Milkweed (Euphorbiaceae) is common in representatives of the family. Coumarins isolated from plants are colorless crystalline substances, poorly soluble or completely insoluble in water, easier in alcohol, well soluble in organic solvents (ether, chloroform, etc.). If coumarins are in the form of glycosides, their solubility in water increases. But the aglycones of glycosides hydrolyzed under the influence of diluted sulfuric acid are insoluble in water, but they dissolve well in alcohol and organic

solvents. The cruciferous plant belongs to the Apiaceae family, and dark resin (glue) is extracted from the inner part of the root, and the substances contained in the manashu resin (glue) are mainly used in the treatment of diseases. Now we will perform a qualitative reaction to determine the presence of coumarin in the Kovrak plant. Take 1-2 g of the dried and crushed product, put it in a flask, pour 5-10 ml of alcohol on it and leave it for 4 hours. Then the flask is heated at a temperature of 50°C for 2-3 minutes. The solution is filtered and a few drops of 5% alkali solution are added to it and heated in a water bath for a few minutes. If there are coumarins in the alcoholic extract, they form coumarins and, as a result, the solution is colored yellow (light yellow). It will be possible to conduct qualitative reactions to coumarins by dividing the yellow (light yellow) solution in an alkaline medium into 2 test tubes.

Conclusion: Kovrak plant is grown in our country and exported to foreign countries. In other countries of the world, the composition of this plant is identified and used as a medicine, although we buy medicines from abroad for the treatment of the above-mentioned diseases. This product, which is taken away from us, will be returned to us at a high price, the composition of the blanket has been determined in other countries, why can't we do this? There are a lot of such questions, and as an answer, we can show results only by determining the composition of this plant and determining how it is used for which disease.

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